

A Case Study on Boston Tea Party

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Introduction :

After the conclusion of the Seven Years' War in 1763, the British Empire was in financial distress. Though the British had won the war, they had spent vast amounts of blood and treasure in the process. At the end of the war, the British Parliament sought to replenish its depleted coffers by taxing the North American colonies. When the British Prime Minister, Lord North, proposed the Tea Act in May 1773, he was not even thinking of the North American colonies, but rather of the East India Company, which had assumed control over India. In exchange for the power to appoint its governors, North loaned the company £1.5 million the equivalent of about \$270 million today. Also, North granted the company a monopoly on the right to sell tea in the North American colonies.

Background of Boston Tea Party :

As the British authorized the shipment of thousands of pounds of tea to its colonies in North America Boston, Charleston, New York City, and Philadelphia colonial tea merchants protested.

In Boston, Governor Thomas Hutchinson, a pro-British Loyalist, demanded that the ships be allowed to dock and that colonial merchants pay the duties on the cargo. Boston was the center of colonial revolutionary fervor, and its radicals did not take kindly to Hutchinson's demands. The Sons of Liberty, a secret society formed by radical colonists to protest British taxation policies after the passage of the Stamp Act in 1765, spearheaded the opposition to the Tea Act. On December 16, 1773 at Griffin's Wharf, a group of approximately 50 Bostonians disguised as Native Americans boarded the ships *Beaver*, *Dartmouth*, and *Eleanor*, and proceeded to dump 342 crates of tea into the Boston harbor. In doing so, they destroyed almost 10 thousand pounds sterling worth of tea worth about \$1.7 million today that belonged to the British East India Company. The incident, referred to at the time by John Adams as the Destruction of the Tea, would not become known as the *Boston Tea Party* for another fifty years.

Key Event for the Revolutionary War :

The Boston Tea Party was the key-event for the Revolutionary War. With this act, the colonists started the violent part of the revolution. It was the first try of the colonists, to rebel with violence against their own government. The following events were created by the snowball effect. There, all the colonists realized the first time, which they were treated wrong by the British government. It was an important step towards the independence dream, which was resting in the head of each colonist. They all fled from their mother country to start a new life in a new world, but the British government didn't give them the possibility by controlling them.

The events leading to the Boston Tea Party began already ten years before (1763), when the English won the French-and-Indian War. The king of Britain passed taxes on the colonies to make up for the loss of money because of the war. He did it in a line of acts, called the Sugar Act (tax to protect and secure the colonists) and the Stamp Act (tax on all licenses, newspapers and business papers). The colonists reacted with protests against those acts, what made the British Parliament to repeal the taxes within 5 months. Then they (the government) passed taxes on lead, paint, paper and tea. These acts were called the Townsend Duties, but the colonists called them the "Insidious Acts". Mass meetings were held and people tried to influence others not to buy English imported goods anymore. In the end the parliament removed all the taxes except for tea. Actually the colonists easily didn't want to

accept, to pay taxes to a government; they don't really belong to anymore. Although this tax on the tea cost a colonial family just pennies a year. Sam Adams, a kind of leader of the colonists, figured out, that the tax could be raised or lowered by the parliament at will. (Sam Adams: "The power to tax is the power to destroy!").

He also pointed out, that the colonists had no representation in the Parliament, and that they can't be taxed without having a representation in there, to care for their interests and wills. However, most people drank tea smuggled in from the Netherlands, so they didn't care very much whether the parliament raises or lowers the taxes. When the East India Tea company realized, that the colonists were drinking cheap, smuggled tea, the Parliament gave them (the company) the monopoly to export tea without paying duties. That way the tea could be much cheaper than the Holland tea, even with the taxes. This act was called the Tea Act, which was of great importance for the following Boston Tea Party.

The colonists reacted to this act by holding meetings to discuss it. Supporter of the revolution (just to name some of them: John Adams, John Hancock, Dr. Joseph Warren) wrote letters of protest to the government's officials, but they didn't achieve anything. The tea ships arriving in Boston still had to pay the full British tax. In September, 1773, a radical group of colonists found out, that three East India tea cargo ships, laden full with tea, were heading for Boston under full sail. They knew that if the ships got unloaded and the tax would be paid, it would be a crushing defeat.

The same radical group wanted to make the agents of the East India Company resign from their job in front of a big crowd, but this part didn't work. Over the following weeks speeches in form of propaganda were made, to get all colonists informed about the events. People even quit drinking tea (what they did for their whole life) and started drinking coffee.

The reactions of the British Government were called the "Intolerable Acts". 4000 British soldiers closed the Boston Harbor, so that Boston couldn't get any food or other important goods. But this act failed its mission, because the other colonists sent the Boston citizens food and other life important goods. They also created a militia to protect themselves of the British army. They also weren't allowed to hold any meetings in Boston anymore. These tries to get the colonies under their control again were the last ones with a view of success.

Conclusion :

The Boston Tea Party, which involved the willful destruction of 342 crates of British tea, proved a significant development on the path to the American Revolution was known to contemporaries as the Destruction of the Tea, was a direct response to British taxation policies in the North American colonies. The British response to the Boston Tea Party was to impose even more stringent policies on the Massachusetts colony. The Coercive Acts levied fines for the destroyed tea, sent British troops to Boston, and rewrote the colonial charter of Massachusetts, giving broadly expanded powers to the royally appointed governor.

References :

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boston_Tea_Party
- Marissa Moss (2016) : *America's tea parties: not one but four!* : Boston, Charleston, New York, Philadelphia. Abrams Books for Young Readers, p. 20, ISBN 978-1613129159.
- “*Boston Tea Party - United States History*”, Encyclopedia Britannica, Retrieved July 11, 2020.